

Conflict Management and Employee Turnover in Selected Private Universities in Anambra State

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Abstract:

The study examined conflict management and its influence on employee turnover. The objective of the study was to determine the relationship between conflict, management and employee turnover. The study employed descriptive survey design to generate data which were analyzed using product moment correlation coefficient, which establish the extent of correlation between two variables. Subject for the study were one hundred and eighty two. It was discovered that conflict management has a positive influence on employee turnover. Locating the core conflict helps management to seek for resolutions that work and management should concentrate on developing innovative, structural and procedural changes that encourage communications and a broad corporate focus.

Keywords: Conflict Management, Employee Turnover, Management, Resolutions and Innovatives

INTRODUCTION

The question of employee turnover has come to gain greater attention in this new century. (Capelli, 2000) .The high rate at which employees quit their job especially in private institutions in Nigeria is one of the Problems facing university management in Nigeria. Available evidence indicates that employees quit their job usually as a result of the unsatisfactory situations such as low motivation and poor conditions of service. (Ologunde, Asaolu, Elumilade, 2000).

White (2005) identified job dissatisfaction, errors in employee's selection and poor management as causes of employee turnover. Turnover is often as the indicator of organization's efficiency. (Glebe &Bax, 2004).

Employee turnover is a ratio comparison of number of employees a company or an organization must replace in a given period of time to the average number of total employees. (Muskan, 2013) High turnover often means that employees are dissatisfied with their jobs especially when it is relatively easy to find a new one (Lee, 2008). Hom and Kinicki (2001) found that employees blame work and thus become dissatisfied with their jobs and leads to conflict caused by combined responsibilities of work, family and community. Conflict is an inevitable friction in any work place. But it doesn't have to bring down morale or effect productivity. Conflict is fundamental to the development of any society (Fatile & Adejuwon, 2011) Conflict in the workplace is a painful reality and a key reason for poor productivity and frustration.

Anything that disrupts the office, impacts on productivity or poses a threat to other employees needs addressing. According to Aula and Siira (2010), the degree to which you tolerate a situation before intervention may vary. A manager may not feel it necessary to intervene when a minor exchange of words occurs between employees—unless such an incident becomes a daily occurrence and expands beyond the employees initially involved.

In the university system, it is common for management to have misunderstanding with staff which may be due to administrative misunderstanding. According to Amosa (2004), delegation of authority match with responsibility could lead to feud between boss and subordinate. Also, the school system observes Christ (2009), may have some security lapses which may lead to misunderstanding between management and staff Conflict management in the school system is only good enough when it is proactive. It involves the reduction, elimination or termination of all forms of conflict. Conflict management as identified by (Goldfien & Robbenolt, 2007) are Avoiding, Dominating, Compromising, Collaborating and Accommodating. This study

seeks to question the association between conflict management and its impact on employee turnover in the following universities: Madonna, Tansian and Paul all located in Anambra State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Nigerian higher institutions witness series of organizational conflicts .Many conflicts lead to anarchy. many known conflicts have resulted in protracted disharmony in school staff , interpersonal relationship, disarmed school authorities , clogged channel of progressive communication and rendered institutions of learning ungovernable(Agbonna,2009; Alabi,2002; Oguntuase1999, Olugbile,2005).most violent conflicts in Nigerian higher institutions of learning have been traced to contested bases of citizenship rights, greed, predatorrule, autocracy and unresolved grievances(Oloyede,1999).

Conflict has given rise to distrust among employees and management contributing in hampering smooth effective and efficient administration in the universities. Conflict arises for several reasons. Conflict can arise out of misunderstanding. Erroneous interpretations of communications and emotions form the basis of many conflicts. Similarly, frustration over a problem may be interpreted by someone else as anger or scorn. Their response may be to avoid working with the person, which aggravates the situation and increases to the level of ongoing conflict.

The other major basis for conflict is due to job dissatisfaction, employees are not promoted at work, there is injustice, employees don't know who to lay their complain to and they are not motivated at work place and this leads to high turnover of employees and the organizational productivity to be low.In order to resolve these, we resort to conflict resolution method using avoiding, accommodating, dominating, collaborating and compromising. Conflict management will help checkmate employee turnover in private universities in Anambra state.

1.3 OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The study examines conflict management and employee turnover as a broad objective.

The specific objective is to determine how conflict management influences employee turnover in private universities.

1.4 RESEARCH QUESTION

To what extent does conflict management influences employee turnover in private universities

1.5 RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

H0: conflict management has no significant influence on employee turnover.

H1: conflict management has significant influence on employee turnover.

1.6 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study shall be of benefit to management of respective organizations in conflict management. Particularly, it shall give beneficial recommendations that will help management of universities and all other tertiary institutions. The student researchers will find this work useful in proffering solution to management- employee conflict. The society in general shall benefit also in seeing how best to resolve conflict in work places.

1.7 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study looks at conflict management and employee turnover in three private universities in Anambra State: Madonna, Tansian and Paul.

1.8 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

In the course of this study, it was limited to three private universities in Anambra state. The results will not be generalized to other private universities that were not included in this study. The researcher also encountered the problem of the reluctance of some participants to fill the administered questionnaire because of their busy schedules.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Many people view conflict as an activity that is almost totally negative and has no redeeming qualities while other school of thought accepted it as dysfunctional, destructive and at the same time as a catalyst for change, creativity and production. (Posigha & oghurwu, 2009). The interactions at different levels in the organization tend to result to conflict making. Conflicts however can be useful in gingering employees to work harder or enabling management to achieve certain goals. (Nnabuife, 2009).

Conflict occurs as a result of interaction among people, an unavoidable concomitant of choices and decisions and an expression of the basic fact of human interdependence (Adejuwon & Okewale, 2009). Robbins (2008) in Nnabuife(2009) discussed three transition conflict has passed through, these they termed the traditional view, which explains the belief some people have that all conflict is harmful and must be avoided. The human relations view maintains that conflict is a natural occurrence since it arises from normal human relationship in all forms and levels of organizations. The interactions view insists that conflict is not only positive in organizational relationship but is also for improved and effective performance.

There are several approaches to types of organizational conflicts by Hener, (2010):

- Vertical conflicts occur because the supervisor is always telling an employee what to do and tries to 'micro-manage', while/although he/she should let the employee to do his/her job. This type of conflict exists in organizations where the organizational structure has a high degree of formality;
- Horizontal conflicts occur between employees within the same department, i.e. on the same hierarchical level. These conflicts can manifest themselves for many reasons, such as the different interests/ideas related to distribution of resources;
- Line Staff conflicts occur between support staff and line employees, within a department or an organization;
- Role conflicts can stem from an incomplete or otherwise fallacious understanding of the assignment given to an employee at a specific moment in time.

Human Nature and Conflict Management

Human nature is the human condition outside of organized society or civilization. Conflicts have made management of educational institutions in Nigeria to be the spotlight throughout the country. (Fatile & Adejuwon, 2011). Also observes Certo (2013), the consequences of organizational conflict is the interface between work and organizations experiment with flatter and more decentralized structures. In human conception, conflict is considered as "neither" bad nor good, wrong or right.

The Causes of Conflict in Organizations

When people work together, conflict becomes a part of doing business; it's a normal occurrence in any workplace. Conflict notes Graham (2009), is widely used to describe important differences between individuals or groups of humans. Differences, which result in initiative and creativity, are stimulating for those involved, and such conflict is essential for progress. In general, conflict is a process in which one party perceives that another party is affecting its interest. Conflict has been with us for a long time and people have been writing about it. Personal conflict can take the form of inter role conflict. Also it can take form at the interpersonal level where individuals come into with others, and interorganizational conflict where organizations themselves come into conflict.

Methods of Handling Conflict in an Organisation

Conflict can be managed in different ways but this study will be focusing on conflict resolution. Conflict resolution otherwise known “reconciliation” is conceptualized as the methods and processes involved in facilitating the peaceful ending of conflict and retribution (Wilmot & Jouyce, 2007). According to the dual model by Goldfien & Robbenolt(2007). The dual identifies five conflict resolution styles and strategies that individuals may use depending on their dispositions towards pro-self or pro- social goals.

(1) **Avoidance conflict style**- This is characterized by changing of or avoiding the topic, joking or even denying a problem that exist. Conflict avoidance style is used when an individual has no interest in dealing with the other party. For example, in chinese culture, reasons for avoidance would be to sustain a good mood, protect the avoider and because of philosophical and spiritual reason. (Feng& Wilson,2011). During conflict, these avoiders adopt a wait and see attitude often allowing conflict to phase out on its own without any personal involvement. (Bayazit& Mannix, 2003).

(2) **Accommodating**- In contrast, accommodating or ‘yielding’ conflict styles are characterized by a high concern for others while having a low concern for one’s self. This passive pro- social approach emerges when individuals derive personal satisfaction from meeting the needs of others and have a general concern for maintaining stable, positive and social relationship (Wilmot & Jouyce, 2007).

(3) **Competitive Conflict style** – competitive or fighting ‘ conflict style maximizes individual assertiveness (concern for self)and minimizes empathy (concern for others). Groups consisting of competitive members generally enjoy seeking domination over others and typically see conflict as a win or lose predicament. Fighters tend to force others to accept their personal views by employing competitive power tactics (e.g. argue, insult, accuse, violence) that foster feelings of intimidation (Morril, 1995).

(4) **Collaborating conflict style**- cooperation or collaboration conflict style is typically used when an individuals has elevated interests in their own outcomes as well as in the outcomes of others. During conflict, cooperators collaborate with others ia an effort to find an amicable solution that satisfies all parties involved in the conflict. (Wilmot & Jouyce, 2007) individuals with this type of conflict style tend to be highly assertive and empathetic at the same time.

(5) **Conciliation conflict style** – conciliation or compromising style is atypical of individuals who pose an intermediate level of concern for both personal and others. Compromisers value fairness and in so doing anticipate mutual give and interactions. Compromisers believe this agreeableness will encourage others to meet half way, thus promoting conflict resolution (Van&Ewema, 1994).

Every conflicts holds the opportunity for creating improved processes and developing procedures. accordind to Barker, Kathy, Watson and Kibler (1987), we are familiar with the negative attributes of conflict, avoidance, immobility , violence, inertia. However, notes Burton(1988), conflicts has a positive side brimming with opportunities, conflicts has the ability to foster creativity, higher thinking, better listening skills and change. These in turn provide management with the tools for significant improvement, It is inevitable we will not run into conflict , we can choose to deal with it in a negagative or positive manner.is a key to long term growth and success.

Employee Turnover

This is the rate at which an employee leaves an organization for another, as define by Grace (2012). From organization to organization, crises arise which necessitate employee turnover, which may include: poor communication among workers, poor remuneration as seen by workers, unsafe work environment, job insecurity as well as frosty relationship between boss and subordinate.

There are four types of turnovers: **Voluntary**, is the first type of turnover, which is when an employee self-willingly makes the decision to leave the organization. Voluntary turnover could be a result of a better job offering, staff conflict, and lack of opportunities in career advancement. (Lee, 2008)

The second type of turnover is **Involuntary**, this occurs when the employer makes the decision to discharge an employee and the employee unwillingly leaves his or her position (Lee, 2008)

The third type of turnover is **Functional**, which occurs when a low performing employee leaves the organization. (Lee, 2008)

The fourth type of turnover is called **Dysfunctional**, it is when a high performing employee leaves the organization. (Lee, 2008)

High labour turnover is dangerous as it affects the growth and productivity of an establishment. Scholars believe that a core of experienced workers is necessary for the success of an organization. For experience on the job and in the organization, workers must be stable (Hackett, 1979). In any organization, universities inclusive, in which motivation is low, a number of problems are almost certain to arise. These include: (1) Lack of satisfaction for workers to perform to their full capacity and the organization's human resources will not be optimally utilized; (2) Lukewarm attitude towards assigned duties; (3) Organization's objectives will not be fully realized since there will be poor quality of work.;(4) Staff attrition and high rate of labourturnover is inevitable.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is anchored on perceived organizational support theory. Which began with the observation that if managers are concerned with their employees commitment to the organization. Employees are focused on the organization's commitment to them.

Organizational support theory (pos) holds that in order to meet Socio emotional needs and to assess the benefits of increased work effort, employees form a general perception concerning the extent to which the organization values their contributions about their wellbeing. Such perceived organizational support (pos) would increase employees' feet obligation to help the organization reach its objectives, their affective commitment to the organization and their expectation that improved performance would be rewarded. Behavioural outcomes of pos would include increase in inrole and extra-role performance and decreases in stress and withdrawal behaviours such as absenteeism and employee turnover. (Rhodes& Eisenberger,2002, Eisenberger,Hutchinsom &Sowa,1986;Shore1995)

EMPIRICAL STUDIES

According to Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development (2014), a study on Human Resource Practitioners in organizations indicates that almost half (44%) of the respondents reported that disputes are managed continually at work place, managers spend 3.4 hours weekly to solve problem and managing conflict. Nwagu (2014), studied causes of conflict and its effect on employee turnover in tertiary institutions using 100 workers of Anambra State University only and Madona University, 78 (78%) noted that administrative conflict are the security challenges constitute major problem of conflict in universities with 22 (22%), stating that academic and land issues constitute major causes of conflict.

Udensi (2013), studied the cause of employee turnover in the university of Nigeria. Of the 50 workers of the departments of Mathematics, Statistics and Geology studied, 40 (80%), agree that frosty relationship between boss and subordinate constitute major reason of employee turnover, with 10 (20%) stating that personal issues constitute major reason for employee turnover.

Badaru (2013), studied the reason employee turnover in the Kano State University Wudil. Of the 80 employees in the faculty of the management sciences, 50 (62%), agree that high handedness by management induces employee turnover while 30 (38%) stated that personal dissatisfaction mostly need to employee turnover.

Fatile & Adejuwon (2011) examined conflict and conflict management in tertiary institutions; the case of Nigerian universities. It was found that conflict is generally perceived as unwholesome because of its destructive manifestations and there is need to avoid it.

Ologunde, Asaolu & Elumilade (2011) in their study labour turnover among university teachers in southwestern Nigeria proffered that improved conditions of service will immensely motivate employees towards better performance. Salaries and fringe benefits should be enhanced and made relevant to prevailing economic circumstances by reviewing them periodically. Efforts should be made at improving the overall welfare of teachers, including through provision of good accommodation and medical facilities to maintain a low turnover.

Tom & Huckman (2008) carried out a study on Managing the impact of employee turnover on performance, in which they investigated the magnitude and direction of turnover's effect on operating performance. The study indicates that an employee's departure would have a large effect on performance because the organization loses an employee with substantial experience.

Ola & Oyibo (2000) observed that the current orientation is that conflict is an inherent aspect of every organization that dysfunctional conflict should be resolved while functional conflict should be accepted and in fact encouraged if its level is too low in the organization.

The study has shown that conflict is a process and it is inevitable because individual has interdependent relationship. There is no doubt that just as conflicts abound in human beings so it is in tertiary institutions. A major factor militating against organizational productivity is conflict between employees or groups of activities in the organization. These studies focus more on the cause of high turnover among employees thereby creating a gap. This study closes this gap by concentrating on administrative conflict as the major cause of turnover. This study therefore, examines the effect conflict management on employee turnover rate.

METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study is a survey design because it uses research questionnaire to get data from the field respondents. The respondents are employees of the universities of study.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The population of the study is one hundred and eighty two and is gotten from the personnel department of the institutions studied and it comprises of senior officers of the institutions of study. The distributions are as follows;

University Name	Population
Madonna University.	98
Tansian University.	33
Paul's University	51
Total	182

Source; personnel department

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The data for the study was collected from primary source. Copies of questionnaire were constructed, distributed and collected by the researcher. The questionnaire was structured on objective response on each item of the likert five point scale of strongly agreed- 5 points, agree- 4 points nil -3 points ,disagree_ 2 points strongly disagree-1 point.

VALIDITY OF INSTRUMENT

The validity of a measuring instrument refers to the degree to which an instrument measures what is supposed to measure (Carmines & Zeller, 1979). The instrument was tested and approved for use by the supervisor and it goes with what the study intends.

QUESTIONNAIRE RELIABILITY TEST

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.712	12

Source: SPSS Ver. 22

From the table above, the computed Cronbach/Coefficient Alpha value was .712, N = 12, as suggested by most studies α value greater than .70 indicates a strong degree of internal consistency.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 DATA PRESENTATION

Table 1: Schedule of Questionnaire Administration

University Name	Questionnaires Administered	Returned
Madonna University.	98	57
Tansian University.	33	28
Paul’s University.	51	36
Total	182	121

Source: Field Survey (2015)

From the table above, the number of duly completed and returned questionnaires is one hundred and twenty one (121); this figure represents approximately sixty six 66% of the total distributed questionnaires.

Table 4.2 **Gender distribution of Respondents**

		Frequency
Valid	Female	70
	Male	51
	Total	121

Source. Field survey 2014, SPSS Ver. 22

Table 4.3 Academic Qualification of Respondents

		Frequency
Valid	BSc/HND	89
	MSc/MBA	32
	Total	121

Source. Field survey 2015 spss . Ver. 22

Table 4.4 FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION OF QUESTIONS AND RESPONSES

Table 3: Frequency Distribution					
Question	SA	A	N	D	SD
When a conflict arises, I am usually willing to adjust my priorities to reach a resolution.	78 44.8%	54 31.0%	3 1.7%	28 16.1%	11 6.3%
When someone else thinks they have a good idea I cooperate and help them.	80 46.0%	53 30.5%	5 2.9%	21 12.1%	15 8.6%
I am always willing to consider other people’s opinions, but I make my own decisions.	64 36.8%	73 42.0%	7 4.0%	17 9.8%	13 7.5%
During conflict, I invite more discussion about our difference.	62 35.6%	75 43.1%	2 1.1%	22 12.6%	13 7.5%
When viewpoints are opposed, I generally propose a middle ground.	40 23.0%	50 28.7%	31 17.8%	25 14.4%	28 16.1%
I think it is more important to get along than to win an argument.	57 32.8%	94 54.0%	14 8.0%	4 2.3%	5 2.9%
My expectations were met after i joined the organization.	41 23.6%	69 39.7%	16 9.2%	31 17.8%	17 9.8%
The training programme offered by my organization is a key reason why people join the organization.	68 39.1%	79 45.4%	18 10.3%	9 5.2%	-
The work environment is satisfactory for employees.	82 47.1%	79 45.4%	9 5.2%	3 1.7%	1 .6%
The working hours are satisfactory in the organization.	81 46.6%	80 46.0%	5 2.9%	8 4.6%	-
I am stressed at work.	91 52.3%	76 43.7%	7 4.0%	-	-
I am happy with my salary and nature of my job.	92 52.9%	66 37.9%	7 4.0%	6 3.4%	3 1.7%

Source: Field Survey (2015)

4.2 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF QUESTIONS

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
When a conflict arises, I am usually willing to adjust my priorities to reach a resolution.	174	1.00	5.00	3.9195	1.29667
When someone else thinks they have a good idea I cooperate and help them.	174	1.00	5.00	3.9310	1.32380
I am always willing to consider other people's opinions, but I make my own decisions.	174	1.00	5.00	3.9080	1.21296
During conflict, I invite more discussion about our difference.	174	1.00	5.00	3.8678	1.23990
When viewpoints are opposed, I generally propose a middle ground.	174	1.00	5.00	3.2816	1.38781
I think it is more important to get along than to win an argument.	174	1.00	5.00	4.1149	.86586
My expectations were met after i joined the organization.	174	1.00	5.00	3.4943	1.29359
The training programme offered by my organization is a key reason why people join the organization.	174	2.00	5.00	4.1839	.81926
The work environment is satisfactory for employees.	174	1.00	5.00	4.3678	.71507
The working hours are satisfactory in the organization.	174	2.00	5.00	4.3448	.74999
I am stressed at work.	174	3.00	5.00	4.4828	.57626
I am happy with my salary and nature of my job.	174	1.00	5.00	4.3678	.85497
Valid N (listwise)	174				

Source: SPSS Ver. 22

4.3 TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

HYPOTHESIS ONE

H₀: Conflict management has no significant influence on employee turnover

H₁: Conflict management has significant influence on employee turnover

Interpreting Pearson Correlation Result:

A positive correlation means that as one variable increases in value, the second variable also increase in value. Similarly, as one variable decreases in value, the second variable also decreases in value. Likewise, a negative correlation means that as one variable increases in value, the second variable decreases in value.

Table 5: Correlations

		CM	ET
CM	Pearson Correlation	1	.246**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	174	174
ET	Pearson Correlation	.246**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	174	174

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Ver. 22

Result Summary:

Pearson correlation coefficient was computed to determine the relationship between conflict management and employee turnover. From the table above, the Pearson correlation coefficient was .246** (positive), and significant at .001 thus we reject null hypothesis and accept the alternate ‘*Conflict management has significant influence on employee turnover*’.

FINDINGS

The result for the test of hypothesis using Pearson moment correlation coefficient technique reveals that the null hypothesis conflict management has no significant effect on employee turnover is not accepted at 5% critical level. This study reveals that conflict management has a positive significant effect on employee turnover.

We found that there is a relationship between conflict management and employee turnover in the universities studied. This implies that when conflicts come in the university, management should do everything possible to arrest the situation failure of which induces most workers to leave the organization because their private grievances cannot be addressed most appropriately.

CONCLUSION

The study examines the influence of conflict management and employee turnover in private universities. Conflict management influences employee turnover positively. Too often the response to conflict is to deal with the symptoms. Locating the core conflict helps management to seek for resolutions that work. When the spotlight is put on the core issue, opportunities become apparent. Management can concentrate on developing innovative, structural and procedural changes that encourage communications and a broad corporate focus in a typical university system like Madonna, Paul and Tansian.

According to Hempel (1996), company should take a decisive action against any employee or customer who exhibits violent behaviour, threatens violence and/or engages in violence acts. It is your duty to make the workplace conducive and violent-free for all.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are here recommended:

1. The university should have an employee handbook, and accident prevention policy.
2. Employees should be trained in managing conflicts. They should not convert work resources or tools to weapon of attack or defense. An employee who uses his pen or pencil to inflict injury on another employee is liable, and should be sanctioned appropriately for workplace violence.
3. Since employees count on the employer to provide them safe work environment, the university should have in place its zero-tolerance policy for workplace violence, implement training programme and

promote safe conduct of behaviour and work to create an environment that gives employees a peace of mind when at work.

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